

Writing the KAMIT in Qualitative Research made EASY
Instructional Material for Secondary Level Research

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FOREWORD

Research as an applied subject in the Senior High School curriculum remains a challenging area of instruction. Compounding this challenge is the fact that the subject is often taught by teachers whose specializations do not necessarily align with the research discipline. Additionally, research classes are sometimes distributed late in the class program during the second semester, often assigned to those who have not yet received core subject loads.

Characterized by its complex, wordy, and labor-intensive nature, research requires comprehensive instruction to equip students with the necessary skills to produce quality outputs. The same level of support is also essential for teachers who are newly assigned to handle this subject. In response to these challenges, this Instructional Material (IM) titled *Writing the KAMIT in Qualitative Research Made EASY* was developed with two key objectives: (1) to help students produce quality research outputs, and (2) to support new teachers in guiding students toward the completion of their research work.

Aiming to make research tasks more manageable and less overwhelming, the teacher-writer incorporated self-produced Canva videos and PowerPoint presentations into this IM. These materials are designed to support both Grade 11 students and newly assigned research teachers by providing accessible, simplified, and structured content.

This IM was intended to prepare students for their major research outputs, which typically account for sixty percent (60%) of their Performance Tasks. The teacher-writer piloted the use of these materials during E-module classes with selected Grade 11 sections—Andromeda, Leo, and Perseus—and conducted synchronous sessions via Google Meet to assist students in completing their outputs. It is worth noting, however, that limited internet access remained a challenge, with only 15 to 20 students per section able to join the online classes.

As a new generation of educators take on the role of teaching research, this IM may serve as a valuable resource to guide them in developing and delivering lessons with clarity and confidence. Ultimately, it seeks to contribute to the successful completion of students' research outputs and to foster a stronger research culture in the senior high school setting.

Each lesson in this IM is paired with a corresponding video and PowerPoint presentation. To ensure accessibility, all Canva videos and presentations have been uploaded to YouTube as *Unlisted*, allowing anyone with the link to access the content.

Week No.	Topic	Video No.
1	Orientation https://www.canva.com/design/DAE48Uj7D5c/NtWbrWfmSV9YKm9w8BTDg/watch?utm_content=DAE48Uj7D5c&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	1
2	KAMIT Format https://www.canva.com/design/DAE5IHBaZCU/edlA2Y7Oqt9JbL1PhqUGNg/watch?utm_content=DAE5IHBaZCU&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton https://youtu.be/20FVxT6Wbtk	2
2.1	Research Topics – Its Description & Examples https://www.canva.com/design/DAE5OwT2jr8/QLb_rV_RZx9Bmqie-QRuDA/watch?utm_content=DAE5OwT2jr8&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton https://www.slideshare.net/walshandj/choosing-aresearch-topic	3
2.2	Research Title – Its Description & Examples https://www.canva.com/design/DAE5OhhOJRw/hPhdi8w_pgWo_Kpa-O9keg/watch?utm_content=DAE5OhhOJRw&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton https://youtu.be/SgO7i4azcs8	4
3	Background of the Study https://www.canva.com/design/DAE6Gyr44ac/O8xRHpBROM4rJpKm40evjg/watch?utm_content=DAE6Gyr44ac&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton https://youtu.be/XypPNOLQZWc	5

3.1	Objectives of the Study & Problem Statement https://www.canva.com/design/DAE6IDoWd7o/hR66wS6PmuMENGjmj0KoNQ/watch?utm_content=DAE6IDoWd7o&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	6
3.2	Research Questions https://www.canva.com/design/DAE5c8FC HE/U9WkQqDPhMiYUpAQwFhk-A/watch?utm_content=DAE5c8FC HE&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton https://youtu.be/71-GucBaM8U	7
4	Scope, Limitations, & Significance of the Study https://www.canva.com/design/DAE7Z0Y7Ukk/dbVvAysTW7v3GXu6vKIHA/watch?utm_content=DAE7Z0Y7Ukk&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	8
5	Method & Participants – PPT https://www.canva.com/design/DAE6qwfvgCo/CT54KlevwpyLKnTD2ZKswg/view?utm_content=DAE6qwfvgCo&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	9
5.1	Sources of Data – PPT https://www.canva.com/design/DAE6rlnxMk8/6anluWDsATbxwzXqAdDE6Q/view?utm_content=DAE6rlnxMk8&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	10
5.3	Proposal Presentation https://www.canva.com/design/DAE7eaVaoYs/whf4Xji8zSAqPeAE04EGA/watch?utm_content=DAE7eaVaoYs&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	11

6	Proposal Revision; Rechecking – Literature Review; Citing Sources; References https://www.canva.com/design/DAE8gQaA38o/BaGLJgOyxstRxklt8Lbnw/watch?utm_content=DAE8gQaA38o&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	12
7	Important Writing Secrets https://www.canva.com/design/DAE8pQCxEbU/esi7xmZmhZP0zEEivKklLw/watch?utm_content=DAE8pQCxEbU&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	13
8	Re: Research Design: Choosing Your Data Collection Method https://www.canva.com/design/DAE8sERO6T4/2XzC4B7lhtkG4EualDdQEw/watch?utm_content=DAE8sERO6T4&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	14
9	Re: Quantitative Research vs. Qualitative Research https://www.canva.com/design/DAE_1ELKa4c/FVGNtaK6zuTA-YfiBeEMBg/watch?utm_content=DAE_1ELKa4c&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	15
9.1	Ethical Consideration https://www.canva.com/design/DAE_5o3K72E/HM9iPbM55_zAug_bM5EKzQ/watch?utm_content=DAE_5o3K72E&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	16
10	Coding Qualitative Data https://www.canva.com/design/DAE_5IWbLaA/5HMTGNts2Tqtv0nftD1VWQ/watch?utm_content=DAE_5IWbLaA&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton	17

The abovementioned videos and PPTs had been uploaded to the **XEPTO Learning Management System**. Unfortunately, the three (3) Grade 11 sections were hesitant to be enrolled in the LMS, Hence, the said videos were viewed within the Synchronous Classes to at least make the teacher sure they have viewed and learned from them.

This **IM** was accomplished within the weekly schedule of classes this second semester; so, the teacher-writer uploaded her lessons on weekly basis. The lessons here just augmented the ones already provided in the Weekly Learning Activity Sheets [LAS] where forty percent [40%] written output was based. Therefore, this IM specifically targeted the students' Performance Task [60%].

Course: KAMIT Research Format x +
 https://bnhs.xeptoeducation.com/course/view.php?id=254

BNHS

Parts of the KAMIT
 Mark as done

About KAMIT

- Abstract
- Keywords
- Introduction
- Objectives of the Study
- Research Questions
- Scope
- Limitations
- Significance of the Study
- Method
- Participants
- Instruments
- Data Collection Procedure
- Head of Consultation
- Results & Discussion
- Conclusion & Recommendations
- References

Note:
 The succeeding topics details how each part will be written.

1. Practical Research 1 Orientation - Week 1

PR1 Orientation - Week 1
 Mark as done

PR1 on Week 1 Orientation presents the Weekly Submission Schedule, Grading System, ALPAS Research, & Research Rubrics.
 *This ALPAS is the basis for the students Performance Task equivalent to 60%.
 *The other 40% Written Output would come from the Weekly LAS [Learning Activity Sheets] provided to them earlier.

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2. KAMIT Format - Week 2

KAMIT Research Format - Week 2
 Mark as done

The First Parts of the KAMIT Format are discussed here - Abstract, Keywords, Introduction, Objectives of the Study, Problem Statement, Research Questions, & inclusion of the Title description.
 The Activity provided in the video sets each group in the preparation of their Research Proposal.

Abstract - Week 2
 Mark as done

This video provides tips on Writing the Abstract to be finalized after they had already completed their entire research.

BNHS-SHS KAMIT Sample Format - Week 2
 Mark as done

The sample ALPAS Format helps students into its detailed parts. Let them see and study how it is done & completed.

[Help](#)

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3. TOPICS - Its Description & Examples - Week 2.1

Topics - Its Description & Examples - Week 2.1
 Mark as done

Examples of Topics & its Descriptions are provided in order to acquaint students of the Topics in Qualitative Research. Let the Activity in the video help them arrive at the right choice of topic.

Choosing a Research Topic by Walsh - Slideshare
 Mark as done

Let these slides better help students to choose their Research Topic.

4. TITLE - Its Description & Examples - Week 2.2

Title - Its Description & Examples - Week 2.2
 Mark as done

Help

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Examples of Research Titles are presented here for students to study & analyze. Their analysis of how Titles are written would help them create their own.

Research Title - Week 2.2
 Mark as done

The video provides tips on Writing the Research Title. Let this help students write their own Research Title.

5. BACKGROUND of the STUDY - Week 3

Background of the Study - Week 3
 Mark as done

Ways on How to Write the Background of the Study are discussed here.

Background of the Study & Problem Statement - Week 3
 Mark as done

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BNHS

The video on Writing the Background of the Study provides tips to help them write their own.

6. Objectives of the Study & Problem Statement - Week 3.1

Objectives of the Study & Problem Statement - Week 3.1
Mark as done

Students are tasked to study how Objectives of the Study & Problem Statement are stated.

Concept Paper
Mark as done

Let the format be followed in the Concept Paper.

7. RESEARCH QUESTIONS - WEEK 3.2

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Research Questions - Week 3.2
Mark as done

This topic on Writing the Research Questions would help students formulate their own.

How to Develop a STRONG Research Question - Scribbr
Mark as done

The video provides a brief yet informative tips on Writing the Research Questions. Let this guide/assist them in formulating theirs.

8. SCOPE, LIMITATIONS, & SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY - 4

Scope, Limitations, & Significance of the Study - Week 4
Mark as done

Let the presentation of the the Scope, Limitations, & Significance of the Study help students write these parts of the research study.

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9. METHOD & PARTICIPANTS - Week 5

Method & Participants for Research Proposal - Week 5
Mark as done
The content of Method & inclusion of the topic on Participant/s are presented here.

Method & Participants for Research Proposal - Week 4 (copy)
Mark as done
Let this lesson on Method & Participants assist students on their Research Proposal preparation.

How to Create STRONG Research Design - Week 4
Mark as done
Let the video add clarity in determining the Research Design.

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10. SOURCES OF DATA - Week 5.1

Sources of Data - Week 5.1
Mark as done
Let this Sources of Data assist students work on their Research Project.

11. PROPOSAL PRESENTATION - Week 5.2

Research Proposal Presentation 5.2
Mark as done
Let students present their proposals and have some critique the written outputs.

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TOPIC 12

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12. Proposal Revision; Rechecking - LITERATURE REVIEW; CITING SOURCES; REFERENCES - Week 6

Proposal Revision; Literature Review; Citing Sources; References - Week 6
 Mark as done

Let this Literature Review Lesson with inclusion of Citing Sources & References ease up student's Proposal Revision.

13. Important Writing Secret - Week 7

Important Writing Secret - Week 7
 Mark as done

Let this Video Lesson guide students in the interconnections of their sentences into paragraphs and paragraphs within the different sections of their research proposal.

Help

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14. Re: Research Design: Choosing Your Data Collection Method - Week 8

Research Design: Choosing Your Data Collection Method - Week 8
 Mark as done

Let this video reiterate the topic - Choosing the Data Collection Method help students decide on their data collection processes.

Research Design: Choosing Your Data Collection Method
 Mark as done

The video on **Research Design: Choosing Your Data Collection Method** helps students with their own data collection method.

15. Re: Quantitative Research vs. Qualitative Research - Week 9

Quantitative vs. Qualitative Research - Week 9

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BNHS

15. Re:Quantitative Research vs. Qualitative Research - Week 9

Quantitative vs. Qualitative Research - Week 9
 Mark as done

Let this video help students clarify the kind of research they will use.

Quantitative vs. Qualitative Research
 Mark as done

The video clarifies the difference between quantitative and qualitative research. Let this help students with their research completion.

16. Ethical Consideration - Week 9.1

Ethical Consideration - Week 9.1
 Mark as done

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16. Ethical Consideration - Week 9.1

Ethical Consideration - Week 9.1
 Mark as done

Let this study guide confirm how well the students have written their Ethical Consideration.

Ethics in Research
 Mark as done

Let the video guide students in their Ethical Consideration statement.

17. Coding Qualitative Data - Quarter 4 - Week 1

Coding Qualitative Data - Quarter 4 - Week 1
 Mark as done

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17. Coding Qualitative Data - Quarter 4 - Week 1

Coding Qualitative Data - Quarter 4 - Week 1
Mark as done

Let this study guide familiarize students on the QLR Coding System.

Video 1 - What is Open, Axial, and Selective Coding ?
Mark as done

The video familiarizes students to the Open, Axial, and Selective Coding.

Video 2 - How to Analyze Qualitative Data for an Interview/Semi-Structured Interview
Mark as done

The video presents how QLR Coding could be done with data from Interview/s.

Video 3 - Beginners Guide to Coding Qualitative Data

Help

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Coding Qualitative Data - Quarter 4 - Week 1

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Mark as done

The video presents how QLR Coding could be done with data from Interview/s.

Video 3 - Beginners Guide to Coding Qualitative Data
Mark as done

PRI students as beginners could get hints from this video on Coding the QLR.

Help

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Grateful acknowledgement is given to the following sources used in this Instructional Material – *Writing the KAMIT in Qualitative Research made EASY*. <https://www.canva.com>

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Abstract video -- <https://youtu.be/20FVxT6Wbtk> <https://www.dictionary.com> Image of

Keywords from Microsoft Bing <https://studyclerk.com>

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<https://www.bing.com/videos/search?q=writing+research+title&docid>

Notes from "Making Research Life Story Telling, Closer to the Heart" shared by Dr. Ruth M. Balajadia-Ducut - January 16-18, 2020.

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<https://tinyurl.com/Coding2-Lilia>

<https://tinyurl.com/Coding3-Lilia>

<https://tinyurl.com/Coding-Video1-Lilia>

<https://tinyurl.com/Coding-Video2-Lilia>

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Wa-Mbaleka S., & Gladstone K. (2018). *Qualitative research for senior high school*. Cavite: Oikos Biblios Publishing House.

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<https://www.bing.com/videos/search?q=research+questions&view=detail&mid>

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<https://tinyurl.com/Ethics-Lilia>

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<https://tinyurl.com/Coding2-Lilia>

<https://tinyurl.com/Coding3-Lilia>

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<https://tinyurl.com/Coding-Video2-Lilia>

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